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Concerned work package leader: Anne M. Dijkstra, UTwente

Task leader: UTwente

Authors: Anne M. Dijkstra, Anouk de Jong (Utwente)

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ENJOI - Engagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication

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QUALITY ASSURANCE

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we arranged an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the work package leader (formicablu). All partners contributed and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the final version was submitted to the project coordinator for a final review and validation.

DISCLAIMER

This report contains original, unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. It builds upon the experience of the team and related work published on this topic. Acknowledgement of previously published material and others' work has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. The views and opinions expressed in this publication are the authors' sole responsibility and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission and the Research Executive Agency (REA), that are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information here contained.

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SUMMARY

A continuous evaluation was designed to, first, collect data about the process of engaging multiple stakeholders and, second, gather views of the participating stakeholders about the collected and refined Standards, Principles and Indicators and, more broadly, hear their views on quality of science journalism and science communication.

A mixed methodology was applied. Before the Engagement Workshops (EWs) and Labs, a short evaluation questionnaire was handed out to all participants. After the EWs and Labs, interviews were conducted with a selection of participants. In addition, observations from each activity were collected. The instruments for the analysis were developed collaboratively.

The main conclusions regarding the process of engaging multiple stakeholders are that both the EWs and the Labs were professionally organised. The co-creation workshops enabled in-depth discussions which contributed to the development and the refinement of the list of SPIs. In addition, participants valued the workshops which contributed to reflection on the participants' own professional development as well.

Main conclusions regarding participants' views on quality of science journalism and science communication, and the SPIs as guiding principles were that both fields of science journalism and science communication can benefit from discussions and reflection on quality. The list of SPIs offer a valuable guideline, with various fields prioritising different standards or principles. Promotion of the SPIs as guidelines is suggested to enable implementation of quality criteria in work. Science journalism professionals prefer workshops or meetings, while science communication professionals value trainings and courses the most.

Recommendations, in sum, therefore, are to share learnings from the engagement and co-creation processes for future workshops; to promote the SPIs as guidelines for professional development and to organise means where stakeholders can discuss, reflect on, or receive training on quality of science journalism and science communication.

PROJECT OVERVIEW

ENJOI (ENgagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication) is exploring and testing engagement as a key asset of innovation in science communication distributed via media platforms, with a strong focus on journalism.

Through a combination of methodologies and in collaboration with producers, target users and stakeholders of science communication, ENJOI is co-creating and selecting a set of standards, principles and indicators (SPIs) to produce a Manifesto for Outstanding Open Science Communication (OOSC). Therefore, ENJOI has deployed a series of actions via Engagement Workshops (EWs), Labs, field and participatory research, evaluation and testing phases.

ENJOI has also built an Observatory as its landmark product to make all results and outputs available to foster capacity building and collaboration of all actors in the field. The Observatory, currently hosted within the project website, will evolve into an independent product bound to remain online and actively nurtured well beyond the project end. Furthermore, the [ENJOI Observatory](#) will be integral to the [COALESCE](#) project, recently funded under the Horizon Europe scheme to build the European Competence Centre for Science Communication.

The ENJOI Observatory will provide useful insights, resources and tools to support science and generalist journalists in their work. ENJOI is working in four countries: Belgium, Italy, Portugal and Spain, considering different cultural contexts.

ENJOI's ultimate goal is improving science communication by making it more consistently reliable, truthful, open and engaging. Contextually, ENJOI will contribute to the active development of critical thinking, digital awareness and media literacy of all actors involved in the process.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the arguments for the need of ENJOI is that ‘now more than ever before, science communication is a key factor in facilitating democratic deliberation and in fighting misinformation’ (Grant Agreement, 2020). In addition, one of the premises of the project is that fostering engagement in science journalism and science communication can be a key factor in finding out how to innovate science communication and science journalism. As argued, engagement processes can combine the power of communities and better respond to and reflect community needs as well as help increase media literacy (Grant Agreement, 2020). At the same time, understanding the engagement processes helps in understanding better how to deal with communicating about science and, therefore, a continuous evaluation approach was proposed to learn from the activities in ENJOI.

In ENJOI, a series of Engagement Workshops (EWs) and Labs were organised with a diverse range of participants representing the quadruple helix stakeholders. The participants were, for example, communication producers and users, science and data journalists, communication and dissemination experts, citizen science practitioners, media editors, cross-sectional experts, local activists, teachers, students, researchers (scientists), decision-makers, and policymakers. The EWs and Labs were held in four countries, Italy, Spain, Portugal and Belgium, and in local languages or English, as was the case in Belgium.

As described in the ENJOI Grant Agreement, the continuous evaluation (Task 5.2) consisted of two parts. First, a short evaluation questionnaire was handed out to all participants **before** the EWs and the Labs. Second, interviews were conducted with a selection of participants **after** each of the EWs and the Labs. The instruments for the analysis were developed collaboratively. In addition, the partners supported the translation of the questionnaire into the local languages and the answers into English and contributed to the observation forms.

This report describes the findings of the continuous evaluation. In section 2, the methodology is presented in more detail. Section 3 presents the findings, and in section 4 these are discussed. Finally, in section 5, conclusions are drawn, and recommendations for the Observatory are provided.

2. METHODS CONTINUOUS EVALUATION

This section describes the choice for the methodology, the development of the instruments, and the approach for the analysis, and it provides demographic information about the participants.

Mixed-method approach

For the continuous evaluation, a mixed-method approach was chosen with both a quantitative instrument as well as a qualitative instrument. A quantitative method, such as a questionnaire, facilitates making comparisons between countries, media types and roles of the participants. A qualitative method, such as interviews, can catch more of the situation's complexities. Combining both and adding findings from observations to enrich the data helps gather a more in-depth understanding of the participants' views on science communication and science journalism and the engagement process they are asked to participate in. Also, gathering data before and after the activities will provide more insight than only gathering data afterwards.

The methodology was developed in collaboration with the partners and was aligned with the process of designing and implementing the EWs and Labs in WP3 and WP4. The questionnaires were translated into five local languages (Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, French and Dutch). It was not necessary to translate the interview protocols since the interviews were all held in English. Throughout the process, we reflected on the efficacy of the evaluation instruments, and the questionnaires were slightly adapted for the Labs while the interviews contained semi-structured questions and therefore allowed for adaptation during the interview.

In both instruments, the participants were consulted regarding their views about the SPIs, their views on the EWs and Labs and their views on the quality and reliability of science communication. Specific research questions, also described in the GA, inquired how engagement can help to improve science communication and how, in their view, engagement works. In addition to the data from the questionnaires and the interviews, we collected observations of the EWs and the Labs to enrich the data. Table 1 below provides an overview of the evaluation instruments, the expected and collected number of respondents or participants and a brief description of the topics in the evaluation instruments.

Table 1: Overview of activities, evaluation instruments, number of participants			
Activities	Evaluation instruments with the expected number of responses (N)	N Collected (gender and age)	Topics
Engagement workshops	<p>Before: Questionnaire in Qualtrics</p> <p>Each EW will have 8 to 15 participants (expected total N will be between 32 and 60)</p>	<p>N Italy = 19 (11 female; 8 male) N Belgium = 14 (8 female; 6 male) N Spain = 13 (10 female; 2 male; 1 preferred not to say) N Portugal = 13 (10 female; 3 male) N total = 59</p> <p>Ages of the respondents ranged between 18 and 64 years.</p>	Views about SPIs; contribution to quality and reliability of science communication; expectations of the EW and engagement process
	<p>After: Interviews</p> <p>Two participants from each EW will be interviewed (total N = 8)</p>	<p>N = 8 (5 female; 3 male). Ages ranged between 26 and 55.</p>	Semi-structured questions about their experiences, topics that raised attention, what learning outcomes do they see; their view on the engagement process, what message they would have to the ENJOI project
	<p>After: Observations</p> <p>Together with the reporting template observations from the EW will be reported (N=4)</p>	<p>N= 4; four observation forms were collected</p>	<p>One of the organisers fills in a template with three types of questions:</p> <p>Practical – which EW, when, how long, how many participants, what background</p> <p>Process – how did participants experience the EW, how was the ambiance, what was remarkable or different, what stood out</p> <p>Content – how can an engagement process contribute to quality and reliability of science communication</p>
Labs	<p>Before: Questionnaire in Qualtrics</p> <p>Each Lab will have 8 to 15 participants (total N will be between 32 and 60)</p>	<p>N Italy = 13 (8 female; 5 male) N Belgium = 2 (1 female; 1 male) N Spain = 4 (3 female; 1 male) N Portugal = 12 (6 female; 5 male, 1 unknown) N total = 31</p> <p>Ages ranged between 18 and</p>	Views about SPIs; contribution to quality and reliability of science communication; expectations of the Lab

		65 years or older.	
	After: Interviews Two participants from each Lab will be interviewed (total N = 8)	N=4* (3 female; 1 male). Ages ranged between 31 and 37. *arranging the interviews was more difficult after the Labs. Several participants agreed to an interview but did not show up, and others did not respond to requests for interviews. Possibly, time restrictions were one of the reasons for limited responses.	Semi-structured questions about their experiences, topics that raised attention, what learning outcomes they see; their view on the engagement process, and what message they would have to the ENJOI project
	After: Observations Together with the reporting template observations from the Labs will be reported (N=4)	N= 4; four observation forms were collected	One of the organisers fills in a template with three types of questions: Practical – which Lab, when, how long, how many participants, what background Process – how did participants experience the EW, how was the ambience, what was remarkable or different, what stood out Content – how can an engagement process contribute to quality and reliability of science communication

More in detail, the following questions were included in the questionnaires (see Table 2). The participants were asked to fill these in via a link provided before the EWs and Labs were held.

Table 2: Questionnaire topics for EWs and Labs	
Topics	Type of question
Background information about the respondents	Closed
Experience in science journalism and science communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Experience in the field ● Roles ● Type of media engaged with 	Open question Open question Open question
Standards, principles and indicators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Experiences ● What type of experiences ● Influence of these experiences 	Five-point Likert scale Five-point Likert scale Five-point Likert scale

Views on science journalism and science communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keywords • Good science journalism and science communication (only EWs) • Trust 	Open question Five-point Likert scale Five-point Likert scale
Expectations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the workshop • On impact • Professional and personal outcomes 	Five-point Likert scale Five-point Likert scale Open question
Advices or suggestions	Open question

The topics and questions for the semi-structured interviews were similar but delved deeper into views after the EWs or Labs and the engagement process during the co-creation workshops (Table 3).

Table 3: Topics and questions for the interviews (for EWs and Labs)
Topics
Background information about the respondents
The participant's experience with science communication and science journalism, type of stakeholder, background in the field and involvement in what media
Views on the EWs or Labs, both expected and afterwards, views on the dynamics of the EWs or Labs
Views on SPIs after the EWs or Labs
Views on what defines quality and reliability of science journalism and science communication
Views on the engagement process, role in improving the quality and reliability of science communication
Views on the partnerships during the EWs or Labs, expected engagement for the future
Advices or suggestions

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was requested at the Ethical Committee of the faculty BMS (Behavioural, Management and Social Sciences) from the University of Twente and granted under number 211134. Respondents to the questionnaire and participants in the interviews were asked to give their consent. Respondents to the questionnaire could consent before entering the questionnaire part. Interviewees could either fill in the informed consent form, which was sent to them beforehand, or they could provide consent on the recording.

Analysis

Analysis of the questionnaire data was conducted in Excel because of the low number of respondents for each country. Mainly, percentages and other descriptive outcomes are reported due to this expected number of responses. Short reports were produced with a summary of the findings for each country, which informed the reporting in the deliverable.

Partners provided translations were needed. Where possible, comparisons per country and gender were made.

Interviews were held online via Zoom and recorded. The interviews were transcribed with the help of transcription software and fully transcribed manually. The transcripts were uploaded in Atlas.ti and coded. The observation forms were added as well. No recordings were made of the EWs or Labs, except for the Lab in Belgium, which took place online to make it easier for participants with a policy background to partake. This recording was not used. Thematic analysis was applied, and where possible and relevant comparisons per country and stakeholder group were made.

Demographic information of the participants at the Engagement Workshops

The Engagement Workshops were organised in a cascade way to enable learning from each other. In all EWs, participants with a varied professional background somehow related to science journalism or science communication could participate. The first one took place on 11 March 2022 in Bologna, Italy, the second in Brussels, Belgium on 29 March, the third in Barcelona, Spain on 28 April, and the fourth in Lisbon, Portugal on 25 May. In total, 59 participants from the four EWs filled in the questionnaire beforehand (see Table 1 above). Of these participants, 39 identified as female, 19 as male, and one person preferred not to say. The ages ranged between 18 years and 65 years. In addition, eight interviews were conducted after the EWs between May and August 2022. Five of these participants were female, three identified as male. The ages of the participants ranged from 26 to 55 years old. Five of the interviewees had backgrounds more related to (science) journalism, while three had backgrounds more related to (science) communication. Their experiences ranged from 5 or 6 years to more than 20 years, which made them all experts. The time it took the respondents to fill in the questionnaire was about 10 minutes, while the interviews lasted between 35 and 60 minutes.

Demographic information of the participants at the Labs

The Labs were also organised in a cascade way to enable learning from each other. In addition, each Lab addressed a specific stakeholder group. The first Lab took place in Bologna, Italy on 27 October 2022 and addressed representatives of different citizens' organisations, teachers and citizens; the second was held in Lisbon, Portugal on 9 November and addressed researchers from different fields, while the third was organised in Barcelona, Spain on 28 November. This one addressed (science) journalists, (science) communicators, social media experts and others working in the science communication field. The last Lab was organised by the Belgian partner in an online format on 7 December

and addressed research funders and policymakers. In total, 31 participants from the four Labs filled in the questionnaire beforehand (see Table 1 above). Of these participants, 18 identified as female, 11 as male, and one person did not provide information. The ages ranged between 18 years and 65 years. In addition, four interviews were conducted after the Labs took place in January 2023. Three of these interviewees were female, and one identified as male. The ages of the interviewees ranged from 31 to 37 years old. The duration of the questionnaire was estimated to be about 10 minutes, while the interviews lasted between 40 and 53 minutes.

3. RESULTS

In this section, results of the data collected before and after the EWs or the Labs are described, concluded with a summary of the main findings.

3.1 Results from the Engagement Workshops questionnaires

Beforehand, as described above, in total, 59 participants from the EWs in Italy, Belgium, Spain, and Portugal filled in the questionnaires. Since the EWs were organised in a cascade way to enable learning from each other, the reporting will also follow the same order where applicable.

Experience in science journalism or science communication

The participants each had a mix of **experiences in the field of science journalism or science communication**. In table 4, the years of experience per country are presented. Most of the participants in each of the EWs had ample experience in the field, which is 5 years or more. In Italy, additionally, 5 participants had no experience at all, as well as one participant in Belgium and Portugal each.

Table 4: Experience in SJ or SC per country / in years	Italy (N=19)	Belgium (N=14)	Spain (N=13)	Portugal (N=13)
Not at all	5	1		1
Less than 1 year		1		
Between 1 and 5 years	1	1	5	3
Between 5 and 10 years	5	5	3	4
More than 10 years	8	6	5	5

The **roles the participants described** varied broadly in all EWs. In *Italy*, they fulfilled roles as expert (e.g. cross-sectional, pharmacy, public engagement), journalist (e.g. investigative, science), editor, science writer, science communicator (more times), science teacher, creative adviser, teacher and content manager). In *Belgium*, the participants had roles as science outreach officer, facilitator in science communication, coach, coordinator science communication, storyteller, science communicator and educator, press officer, researcher doing science communication, teacher in science communication, PhD students in the field. In *Spain*, roles as science communicator (3 times), science communicator specialised in environmental or biomedical topics, science writer, science journalist, disseminator, museologist, fact checker of scientific information, editor, project developer, and science communication researcher were provided. Finally, in *Portugal*, roles as coordinator in science communication, journalist (3 times), investigator, science communicator (2 times),

director of the science for society initiative, public health medical doctor and communicator, scientist, engineer and researcher of science communication were mentioned. In sum, the roles show a rich variety of positions related to the fields of science journalism and science communication which means they brought a rich and varied experience to the discussion. In addition, in a few cases, no experience in the field was reported, but observations show that the view from these participants were respected and valued as well.

On the question about **engagement with media**, either traditional, institutional or social media, respondents *in all countries* reported involvement in traditional media, such as television or radio; in institutional media, for example, websites, brochures, or press releases; and also in social media, of which Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram or YouTube were often mentioned but also TikTok and other social media were reported. Almost all participants reported at least some experience with social media. Only a few participants reported no engagement with any media.

Experiences with Standards, Principles or Indicators

In two closed questions, participants were asked about their **experiences with Standards, Principles and Indicators (SPIs)**. SPIs were the main topic of debate in both the EWs and the Labs. The question was formulated as follows: In the workshop, standards, principles and indicators (SPIs) for good science journalism and science communication are discussed. How much experience do you have with SPIs separately or the three together? The respondents could answer on a five-point Likert-scale ranging from ‘not at all’ to ‘a great deal’. About one-third of all participants had no experience before participating in the EW, followed by a little or a moderate amount of experience by most other participants (see Table 5). Two participants indicated that they had a lot of experience with SPIs beforehand.

Table 5: Experience with SPIs per country	Italy (N=19)	Belgium (N=14)	Spain (N=13)	Portugal (N=13)
Not at all	8	5	5	6
A little	8	3	3	2
A moderate amount	3	5	4	5
A lot		1	1	
A great deal				

Thereupon, the participants were asked in a closed question what that experience entailed. The answers were derived from the ladder of participation probing from more passive to more active participation (Arnstein, 1969, 1975; see also Dijkstra et al, 2012), and ranged

from having read about SPIs, searched for information, discussed SPIs with others, participated in a workshop before or organised a workshop. Participants were free to leave the question open (when having no experience) or answer as they saw fit. They could give more answers. See Table 6. In total, 23 answers were received from participants who had read about SPIs in the past. Furthermore, participants answered 13 times to have searched for SPIs, and 13 times to have discussed the topic, while 7 answers were given that participation in another workshop had taken place. One answer was received of a participant who had organised a workshop about SPIs before. From the *Italian* participants, fewer answers were received. However, *between the countries* the reported answers differed not much. Mainly, more passive experience with SPIs (have read or searched) was reported than active experience with SPIs (have discussed, participated or organised).

Table 6: Type of experience	Italy (N=10)	Belgium (N=19)	Spain (N=14)	Portugal (N=14)
I have read about SPIs in the past	5	7	6	5
I have searched for SPIs online or in other sources		5	4	4
I have discussed SPIs with others	3	4	2	4
I have participated in a workshop about SPIs before	2	2	2	1
I have organised workshops about SPIs before		1		

Finally, the participants were asked if these experiences had influenced them in some way. They were asked to answer four questions: whether these experiences changed their views on science journalism or science communication; have proven useful for work; influenced their professional attitude, or contributed to more confidence in professional competencies. They could answer on a five-point Likert-scale ranging from 'not at all' to 'a great deal'. From each country, the means and standard deviation are reported and discussed (see Table 7). Reported mean answers were found to be highest in *Italy* and lowest in *Portugal* or *Spain*. Past experiences changed views of the participants to a moderate amount in *Italy* and a little in *Belgium*, *Spain* and *Portugal*. These experiences were reported as 'have proven useful' to a moderate amount in *Italy* and *Belgium*, and a little in *Spain* and *Portugal*. The same pattern is visible for influence on professional attitude. Finally, more confidence in professional competences were reported with a moderate amount and a little for *Italy*, and a little for *Belgium*, *Spain* and *Portugal*. In sum, modest influence is reported from past experiences with SPIs.

Table 7: Influence of experiences	Italy (N=10)	Belgium (N=10)	Spain (N=10)	Portugal (N=11)
My experiences with SPIs in the past...	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)

.. changed my views on science journalism and science communication	3.10 (0.94)	2.00 (0.63)	2.30 (1.00)	1.92 (1.19)
... have proven useful in my work	3.10 (0.83)	2.90 (1.22)	2.20 (1.08)	2.55 (1.37)
... influence my professional attitude	3.20 (0.98)	2.90 (1.22)	2.40 (1.28)	2.55 (1.37)
... contributed to more confidence in my professional competences	2.50 (0.67)	2.30 (1.10)	2.30 (1.19)	2.18 (1.11)

Views on science journalism and science communication

Views on science journalism and science communication were asked with three questions. The first question asked to describe good quality science journalism and science communication with the help of three key words. The second question offered a set of seven statements which could be answered on a five-point Likert-scale ranging from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'. A third question explored views on trust with four statements which could be answered on the same scale as the previous question.

From the keywords word-clouds were produced which are shown in figures 1-4. The figures show that words as clarity, rigour and understandable were considered key. These represent how the respondents see science communication. Most words, also as second and third keywords relate to values (e.g., rigour, honesty, transparency) on the one hand, but also concrete indicators (sources, language, target audience) on the other hand.

Figures 1-4: Word-clouds for the first key-word from Italy, Belgium, Spain and Portugal	
Italy	Belgium
Spain	Portugal

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The table 8 below presents the results on respondents' views of good science journalism and science communication. The means for four of the statements were high and above the midpoint of the scale for *all countries*. This means that the respondents agreed to a large extent with the quality of science journalism or science communication described by 'improves when multiple sources are used', 'improves when openness about the sources is given', 'improves when science sources have more experience with reporting' and 'improves when media producers have more experience'. The other three statements have means which are around the mid-point of the scale which means that participants were somewhat more neutral about the statements 'is independent from the speed of reporting', 'depends mainly on the background of the reporter' and 'is independent from the media type'. The responses from the participants from the *four countries* do not differ much from each other, considering the available number of possible respondents, which means that the respondents' notion for good science journalism and science communication is comparable in the four countries.

Table 8: Views of good science journalism and science communication	Italy (N=19)	Belgium (N=14)	Spain (N=13)	Portugal (N=13)
<i>Good science journalism and science communication ...</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>
.. improves when multiple sources are used	4.32 (0.80)	4.14 (0.74)	4.62 (0.84)	4.46 (0.63)
... improves when openness about the sources is given	4.21 (0.52)	4.43 (0.62)	4.31 (0.72)	4.69 (0.46)
... is independent from the speed of reporting	3.00 (0.92)	2.71 (0.80)	3.23 (1.12)	2.69 (1.32)
... depends mainly on the background of the media producer	2.68 (0.80)	2.57 (0.73)	2.85 (1.10)	3.23 (1.05)
...is independent from the media type	2.95 (1.15)	2.50 (1.18)	2.77 (1.37)	3.23 (1.42)
...improves when science sources have more experience with reporting	4.05 (0.89)	3.57 (0.98)	3.77 (0.80)	4.08 (0.62)
...improves when media producers have more experience	4.00 (0.65)	4.07 (0.80)	4.08 (0.62)	4.07 (0.80)

Regarding trust, the table 9 below presents the results on respondents' views of trust in science journalism and science communication. The reported means for all four statements are the highest in *Portugal*, followed by *Spain*, *Belgium* and *Italy*. Most means are above the mid-point of the scale. Thus, trust is higher when 'the topic is presented from different perspectives', 'when reporters are knowledgeable about the topic' and 'the

communication about the topic is transparent'. For the statement 'interests of stakeholders are reported' the *Italian* respondents were least convinced. These answers were just below the mid-point of the scale with quite a high standard deviation. The respondents in the *other countries*, however, also reported high means for this statement.

Table 9: Trust in science journalism and science communication	Italy (N=19)	Belgium (N=14)	Spain (N=13)	Portugal (N=13)
<i>I trust science journalism and science communication when ...</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>
... the topic is presented from different perspectives	3.79 (0.77)	4.00 (0.65)	4.31 (0.82)	4.46 (0.63)
... interests of stakeholders are reported	2.59 (1.24)	4.29 (0.45)	4.23 (0.97)	4.77 (0.58)
... reporters are knowledgeable about the topic	4.26 (0.55)	3.86 (0.91)	4.62 (0.84)	4.62 (0.84)
... the communication about the topic is transparent	4.63 (0.58)	4.29 (0.45)	4.85 (0.36)	4.92 (0.27)

Expectations about the outcomes and impact

Expectations about the outcomes were asked with three statements whether respondents could relate outcomes to their own work, whether outcomes would make sense to the respondents, and whether outcomes would be used for the next step in the project. In Table 10 the responses are provided. Participants in *all countries* agreed to a large agreement with all three statements.

Table 10: Expectations about outcomes	Italy (N=19)	Belgium (N=14)	Spain (N=13)	Portugal (N=13)
<i>I expect that ...</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>
... I can relate outcomes of the workshop to my own work	4.26 (0.55)	4.29 (0.45)	4.62 (0.62)	4.77 (0.58)
... the outcomes will make sense to me	4.21 (0.69)	3.93 (0.80)	4.54 (0.75)	4.31 (0.61)
... the outcomes will be used for the next step in the project	4.32 (0.57)	4.36 (0.72)	4.54 (0.63)	4.69 (0.46)

In addition, views on engaging stakeholders in general and impact were asked with four statements. These were 'it makes sense to consider input from stakeholders such as myself', 'it can inspire new outcomes', 'it will be informative but with little impact' and 'I expect that suggestions formulated in the workshop will serve as relevant input for the upcoming activities' (Table 11). High means are reported for three of the four questions in *all countries*. This means that participants agreed to a large extent with these statements.

However, participants in *all four countries* answered more neutrally to the statement that ‘it will be informative but with little impact’. These answers were just below the mid-point of the scale which can be interpreted as that they were not sure about the impact. However, the statement leaves room for multiple interpretations which makes the exact meaning the respondents gave to the item unclear. In hindsight, this statement could better have been split into two statements ‘it will be informative’ and ‘it will have little impact’ to ensure clearer answers.

Table 11: Views on engaging stakeholders and impact	Italy (N=19)	Belgium (N=14)	Spain (N=13)	Portugal (N=13)
<i>In general, what is your view on engaging stakeholders in such a workshop?</i>	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
It makes sense to consider input from stakeholders such as myself	4.11 (0.57)	4.29 (0.45)	4.62 (0.62)	4.54 (0.63)
It can inspire new outcomes	4.21 (0.52)	4.29 (0.45)	4.85 (0.36)	4.62 (0.49)
It will be informative but with little impact	2.56 (0.68)	2.79 (0.77)	2.31 (0.72)	2.77 (0.89)
I expect that suggestions formulated in the workshop will serve as relevant input for the upcoming activities	4.11 (0.72)	4.41 (0.64)	4.69 (0.46)	4.62 (0.49)

Additionally, in open questions participants' professional and personal expectations were asked. The responses varied within the four countries, but comparable themes were found. In *Italy* answers as broadening perspectives, exchanging experiences, getting inspiration or increasing professional understanding were given in addition to practical outcomes such as contacts, training, and improving skills. Personal outcomes ranged from new contacts, meeting new colleagues and increasing knowledge and confidence, as well as sharing emotions with others in the field. In *Belgium*, getting more information about open science, broadening perspectives, increasing professional insights, getting inspiration, and deliberate science communication were answers, and personal expectations were networking opportunities, contacts, motivation, inspiration and deliberation and dialogue or getting knowledge were reported. In *Spain*, for example, professional expectations related to broadening the participants' perspective, exchanging experiences, getting inspiration or increasing understanding and knowledge of the field. Also, practical outcomes such as getting new tools were expected. Personal outcomes ranged from getting new contacts, new people in the field, to increasing knowledge and confidence in new perspectives. In *Portugal*, professional expectations were to discuss and think about SPIs for work, to build

bridges between journalistic practices and academic approaches, to improve in various ways, to acquire other perspectives, and new knowledge and also to reflect and network which was also mentioned as personal outcomes. Furthermore, learning, expanding networks, increasing competencies, insights and contributing and understanding better how news is produced and making contacts for the future. In sum, although the precise wording differs, expectations in *the four countries* were comparable while answers related to professional and personal experiences often overlapped. Therefore, these two questions were combined in the questionnaires for the Labs.

3.2 Results from the Engagement Workshops interviews

After the EWs, in total 8 interviews were conducted. Thematic analysis was applied and reporting is based on these themes. Results from the observation forms are included in the reporting and provided additional context.

Contexts of the Engagement workshops

The EW in Italy was held with 19 participants in Bologna on 11 March 2022. From the observations, it was reported that the participants, as a group, were complementary to each other, willing to listen to each other and willing to also include views of those with no experience or less experience in the field. In all, a collaborative, enthusiastic and welcoming atmosphere was reported where participants were open to others. The two interviewees had a background as an editor and as a science journalist. Both had ample experience in mainly the science journalism field, which is more than 10 years.

The EW in Belgium was held with 12 participants in Brussels on 29 March 2022. About 19 people had originally registered, but several had to cancel due to COVID-19 infections which meant that most journalists could not attend. As a group, the participants were enthusiastic about the workshop, eager to participate and interested in the topic. They mingled with each other, actively participated, and listened carefully. The two interviewees had a background as head of a communication department dealing with science communication topics, and a background as a public administrator responsible for writing policies, amongst others on science communication, meanwhile also being a lecturer in science communication at the same time. This interviewee is also sometimes involved in research.

In the EW in Spain in Barcelona on 28 April 2022, 14 participants attended. The observations added that the group was open to debate and the members were interested in

the topic and each other's opinions. The participants were enthusiastic about the workshop and participated actively. There was a relaxed atmosphere during the workshop. Of the two interviewees, one had training as journalist and worked in different science journalism jobs for a science news agency but also for the Ministry of science as well as a commercial newspaper, while currently working as a fact-checker. The other interviewee worked as an academic, a PhD student and a practitioner producing multimedia products for education. Both had about 5 to 6 years or more years of experience.

In the final EW in Portugal in Lisbon on 25 May April 2022, 12 participants attended. The observations added that the group had a rich variety of backgrounds and professional profiles. The group was well-balanced regarding age and academic profiles, but not in gender, more female than male participants, which was due to some last-minute cancellations. This diversity and the importance of their participation were acknowledged which made the participants feel part of the conversation from the beginning. They were willing to express their opinions and share their views. The relaxed atmosphere was facilitated by the venue location. Both interviewees had a background in journalism, one as a general journalist, working currently for a fact-checking organisation and the other as a (science) journalist, recently started working as an independent journalist. With 6 years and about 15 years, they both are experts in journalism.

Two main themes

In the analysis, a thematic approach was applied. Therefore, from the interview questions two main themes were distinguished which could be divided in various sub-themes. The first theme relates to the evaluation of the Engagement Workshops in a broader sense. The questions feeding into this theme related to the expectations beforehand, how the EWs were organised and experienced, and the dynamics of the engagement process during the EWs, complemented with views on engagement more generally and views on professional development. The second theme deals with views on what entails quality science journalism or science communication. The questions contributing to this theme related to views on SPIs after the EW and views on the quality and reliability of science journalism and science communication more generally.

Theme 1: Evaluation of the Engagement Workshops

Regarding **expectations** of interviewees, in *Italy* meeting other people, sharing information and hearing from others while also reflecting on the job were mentioned as well as having the opportunity to get updated on developments in the field. In *Belgium* networking and learning from other experts, or curiosity about who to meet were also mentioned. In *Spain*,

expectations related to connecting to other people in the field and meeting others with different backgrounds and who would normally not easily be met, and those with different perspectives on science journalism and science communication. The same type of expectations were also held in *Portugal*, which included talking with people from different backgrounds, expanding networks and connecting with others, while also understanding doing science journalism with more accuracy.

Organisation and experiences during the workshops, according to all interviewees, were very good. The dynamics were very fine and all agreed that the EWs were 'extremely well' organised by people with ample experience (E1). In the workshops, it was possible to build on the ideas of others and complete the process of analysis, which was according to one of the Italian interviewees an interesting way of extracting the best insights. Another said that nice discussions were held without making interviewees tired. Also, disagreement was accepted, and different views were taken into account. The interviewees from other countries agreed with these descriptions, for example, one interviewee found it an inspiring workshop which provided a lot of energy and was both informative and efficient (E7). It was a good occasion to meet a diversity of people (E8), for example, not only those with an academic background but also with journalists, and others outside the bubble (E4), while the timing for the workshop after the pandemic was perfect (E3). For some, it was the first in-person meeting after the lockdowns. Finally, a quote exemplifies the positive atmosphere: "I know that that day gave me such an energy of the speed in which you can work, if you put people together with the right methods. The right means and tools. How you can advance in eight hours, six hours, to a concrete result to the point and an added value" (E7/62).

Also, many compliments were given to the practical organisation. The venues stimulated discussion and interaction which also was included in the design of the EWs. The length was good, or even sometimes longer sessions were suggested (E4). The time to work in groups allowed sufficient discussion (E2). The moderator was mentioned as having an important role in facilitating the discussions, keeping the time and making sure that the groups discussed the given topics.

When asked for **improvements**, various interviewees only came up with suggestions, after probing again or said they had no suggestions for improvements. One advice would be to always include citizens (E2). They are the ones who really know about communicating science, and it is valuable to take completely different views into account. A few

suggestions were to do more with the group, exchange and learn from the other sub-groups during the EWs (e.g. in Spain the groups stayed together for the whole day), or organise more sessions, for example, for only journalists (E5), or one where journalists can explain to researchers how they work. Measuring impact was also suggested, in particular, in relation to the tools for the indicators (E3). One suggestion was to provide a means for developing a *community of practice* where people can meet and share insights with peers (E6). This will impact the quality of science journalism and science communication.

The **composition** of the participants was regarded as adding to each other because of their backgrounds in different professions (E2). In *Belgium*, the wish was that more French-speaking professionals would go to such workshops. This interviewee also explained that there are mainly Flemish-speaking professionals in science communication, and the professional development of science communication in the French-speaking part is less developed. In some EWs, for example, in *Belgium*, interviewees brought in that more journalistic perspective would have been good to add, while in *Portugal*, it was suggested to bring in perspectives from the decision-makers, for example, the news rooms, directors, editors and publishers. People at these levels make the decisions while most journalists won't have the time to go to workshops as the EW (E5). And directors of newsrooms may sometimes even be unaware of the guidelines, the principles and standards that guide the journalism profession (E6).

Generally, **engagement** was considered by some interviewees the only way to learn from each other. As such the engagement process was appreciated and allowing the participants to collaborate was experienced as fruitful (E4). It forces participants to reflect, for example (E1). Engagement, as in workshops, can improve the quality of science communication a lot, via networking, via connecting people. Often, it was said that journalists and communicators work in separate worlds. In addition, engaging participants leads to more knowledge and sharing insights. It also increased visibility towards others. Therefore, such workshops are crucial to do (E3). That engagement can improve science communication was agreed by other interviewees (E7, E8).

The views on engagement via workshops are also related to the **professional attitude or development** of the interviewees. According to one interviewee, it is important to listen to what researchers bring in and look at them as sources for consultation, because journalists do not have the background to understand the information fully. They are not specialists in science since topics differ too much. Meanwhile, in the daily newsroom, there is often no

time for fact-checking with the researchers, however, in fact-checking organisations and long reportages that is possible (E6).

The interviewees with a **journalism background**, more often referred to the time pressure they work in. The daily deadlines make it rarely possible to meet people from the field. Therefore, such meetings as the workshops were valued. And although some suggested organising trainings, others indicated that informal gatherings, workshops as the EW, provide the possibility to discuss and reflect on professional standards in science journalism (E2). Also, the suggestion for a community of practice (E2), or talking with other journalists (E3) was mentioned. Sharing, reflecting, discussing and concluding was interesting for interviewees (E6). In general, regarding their professional development, interviewees with a journalism background reported frequently how they meet and talk about adherence to indicators and standards or principles in practice, for example in informal meetings or in newsrooms, while also ethical codes or the journalism association contribute to stimulating reflection.

Interestingly, interviewees with a **communication background**, referred to more formal means as offering trainings, for example, for scientists to learn about the way (science) journalism works, or for (science) journalists to learn about the process of science (E4) and establish guidelines. Or between countries (E1). Training, which is not yet offered, can provide students with a basic and fundamental approach to the role of science in society and science communication (E8). And share content at a conference (E7).

Theme 2: Views on quality of science journalism and science communication

The second theme deals with views on what entails quality science journalism or science communication. Quality in science journalism or science communication was differently viewed with interviewees with a (science) journalism background compared to those with a (science) communication background. Those **differences** are, for example, as one interviewee said, that 'too often science communication is mistaken for science journalism' (E2). However, science communication cannot be reduced to science journalism. In this perspective, science journalism is one type of science communication which means that for other types of science communication similar analyses are needed. In practice, science journalism is more mainstream and known by people compared to, for example, science education. Or, journalism, can also be understood as a means to do science communication, or as a channel or a tool (E7). One interviewee pointed out that love for the topic does not have to be included in journalism while in a museum or an exhibition this

passion for the science needs to be included (E2).

The differences also mean that SPIs have a different meaning for participants with different backgrounds, and thus quality is derived from different SPIs (E4). Different standards apply, although some may be aligned. Since methodologies within science communication and science journalism differ in context and objectives, standards cannot work as a standard for all (E2). However, standards are useful when talking about quality. Standards and principles are more abstract and indicators can be measured (E2). Meanwhile, these are good instruments to define a framework to work with (E7) and can uplift the quality.

For *science communication*, understandable and correct, are standards or principles reflecting quality, as is simplifying scientific information. Other principles or standards relate to reliability, trustworthiness and openness. One participant said that it is important to put information in context and take multiple aspects into account (E7). Communicating science should be based on facts, and as objective as possible. When multiple articles with studies point in the same direction, this will measure the reliability of information (E7). Reliability and trust can be seen as synonyms, according to one interviewee (E4). While another interviewee added that trustworthiness, as a principle, is something that needs to be built (E8). Related to that, rather how science is conducted than only providing results should be aimed at. A reason to trust science is that science is a collective endeavour. It is part of the collective system, according to one interviewee (E8).

Another interviewee defined quality of science communication as being *honest*, or *transparent*, about what you're saying. Honesty in science communication is important because of the power science communicators hold towards their audiences. It can be measured or reflected in indicators of sufficient sources and bringing in multiple voices in a message. In addition, since science communicators do not hold the same level of knowledge as the researchers themselves, their information needs to be precise and accurate. Therefore, *accuracy* is another principle in science communication.

In *science journalism*, important standards or principles that were mentioned were *transparency*, and *reliability*, e.g. of the information (E5), of *sources*, while *formats* as a standard or principle were also brought in. *Respect for the audience and public* was mentioned as a principle. This interviewee argued that respect and *trust* are different elements. Respect, from a science journalism perspective, was mentioned by several

interviewees, and also means to trust the public, that are the readers (E1), for example, by respecting their previous knowledge and challenging them to go a bit deeper (E6). *Clarity* is defined as trying to transcribe scientific information into popular language and explain the complexity clearly. This means that the principle of *rigour* is key, which was translated by the interviewee as 'super-precise' (E3). To explain a topic can also be done in a visual way, by means of infographics, for example.

In the context of the principles of reliability and transparency, several interviewees referred to the concept from science journalism literature of **source intimacy**. One interviewee noted a too-close relationship between science journalists and researchers which can affect trust in scientific information (E1). When a too-close relationship exists, and journalists become too intimate with their source, it will be impossible for the journalist to criticize the researchers' work when needed. Another interviewee explained how journalists are sometimes supported by research institutes because of their heavy workload, for example, by providing press releases including already ready-made quotations from researchers. The need for a balance when doing so was noted (E7).

Another concept from the literature discussed by the interviewees was **false balance**. Balance was mentioned several times as providing the audience with a variety of different sources and links to the sources, or including different voices. False balance, was specifically discussed in the case of climate change and how the Guardian decided to deal with it by not representing the voice of climate deniers anymore. The Guardian expanded that to the use of standards for pictures accompanying the news. For example, not including polar bears on a piece of ice in the ocean, but rather, for example, picture a fire in the region to represent climate change. Their standards include real and concrete examples (E2). As one interviewee said: journalists cannot be naive, they need to report in a balanced way (E5).

The remarks about providing balance and avoiding false balance, relate to ideas about tasks for journalists to *fight disinformation*. In particular, interviewees with a fact-checking background thought this one or the most important tasks of journalists (E5, E3). Two examples of fighting disinformation were brought up, during the pandemic when scientific information was surrounded with uncertainty, as well as scientific information about food and nutrition. Another task is to *provide context* since most people don't have much time to reflect on all topics (E6).

In several interviews, *ethical codes or ethical guidelines* within the organisation were mentioned as places where SPIs were discussed. In Italy, an association of (science) journalists was mentioned, while in Portugal interviewees were not aware of the existence of such an association. Other places to discuss journalistic standards were the newsrooms. While in science communication contexts trainings provide the place for discussion.

Additionally, in the interviews, various perspectives on the notion of *objectivity* versus *subjectivity* were provided. In particular, interviewees with a journalism background stated that objective reporting was not possible because always the questions determine the perspective on the topic (E6). Or, simplifying information would always lead to some subjectivity. However, when those discussions took place within the engagement workshops, participants tended to disagree with each other, interviewees reported.

Finally, *reliability* was explained by one interviewee as the percentage of experts or studies that support the scientific data (E3), for example, by indicators as a link to the documents, adding original sources to the journalistic piece, but also honesty about the process, and including different voices. Or, another interviewee phrased it as using more than one source, analysing peer-reviewed research articles, and not sensationalising or speculating (E5). Closely related is transparency about getting sources or funding, according to one interviewee (E6), which will lead to more reliability and credibility. Journalists can do that by providing context and giving information that matters to the audience.

3.3 Results from the Labs questionnaires

This section presents the results from the Lab questionnaires. Beforehand, in total 31 participants from the Labs in Italy, Portugal, Spain and Belgium filled in the questionnaires. Although requested, not all participants filled in the questionnaire. Since the Labs were also organised in a cascade way to enable learning from each other, where applicable, the reporting will follow the order in which the Labs took place. In contrast to the EWs where each EWs addressed the same group of participants, the Labs each focused on addressing different stakeholder groups representing the quadruple helix, as is described below.

Experience with science journalism or science communication

The participants each had a mix of **experiences with science journalism or science communication**. In table 12, the years of experience per country are presented. About half of the participants in the Labs combined had no experience or less than a year in the field.

The other participants had experiences ranging from 1 to 5 to more than 10 years. Since the participants represented different stakeholder groups less experience was expected.

Table 12: Experience with SJ/SC in years per country	Italy (N=13) <i>citizens</i>	Portugal (N=12) <i>researchers</i>	Spain (N=4) <i>communication, journalism</i>	Belgium (N=2) <i>policy makers</i>
Not at all	6	3	1	
Less than 1 year			1	
Between 1 and 5 years	1	2	1	1
Between 5 and 10 years		2		
More than 10 years	5	5	1	1

The **roles the participants described** varied since in each Lab a different group was addressed. In *Italy*, where citizens and organisations representing citizens were addressed, the respondents mentioned roles as journalists, teachers, secondary education expert, physics editor, consultant for innovation or expert at an LGBTI+ centre. In *Portugal*, the participants had a background in research and mentioned roles as professors in various topics such as marine archaeology, history, robotics and others, and roles as principal investigator. In *Spain*, where professionals working science journalism and science communication were addressed, roles as project officers or managers and science journalists were mentioned. Finally, in *Belgium* the Lab was held online and included decision-makers and policy makers. Only one respondent responded to this question. This person had a professional background as a communication advisor for a research funding organisation. In sum, the roles that were mainly reported were related to the stakeholder groups the participants belonged to. In some cases, participants' roles aligned with those in the science journalism or science communication field.

On the question about **engagement with media**, respondents *in Italy* reported involvement in traditional media, such as television or radio and printed media; in institutional media, for example, via websites en newsletters, while in social media, the usual media were mentioned as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, YouTube or TikTok, and Whatsapp. In *Portugal*, participants reported experience with traditional media such as printed media and magazines, journals and television, while websites of the institutes or projects related to the institutional level. Most participants were engaged with social media as well. Two participants reported no engagement with any media. In *Spain*, two participants were engaged in media, two were not. Television and radio were mentioned as traditional media, and media for the communication department and museums as institutional media while social media included Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, podcasts and general digital publication means. Finally, in *Belgium* press releases were mentioned as traditional media,

websites and newsletters as institutional media and social media included Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and Instagram.

Experiences with Standards, Principles or Indicators

In two closed questions, participants were asked about their **experiences with SPIs**. On the question of how much experience participants had with SPIs separately or the three together, the respondents could answer on a five-point Likert-scale ranging from ‘not at all’ to ‘a great deal’. In *Italy*, most of the participants had a little or a moderate amount of experience with SPIs (see Table 13). Some participants had knowledge of or even participated in the EW before. One participant had a lot of experience and one had none at all. In *Portugal*, three respondents had no experience with SPIs at all and three had little experience while one person had a great deal of experience. In *Spain*, two respondents had no experience while one person had a little and one reported a lot of experience with SPIs. One of the *Belgium* participants reported no experience at all, while the other reported a moderate amount of experience.

Table 13: Experience with SPIs per country	Italy (N=11)	Portugal (N=7)	Spain (N=4)	Belgium (N=2)
Not at all	1	3	2	1
A little	6	3	1	
A moderate amount	3			1
A lot	1		1	
A great deal		1		

Thereupon, the participants were asked what that experience entailed. As with the questionnaire from the EWs, the answers were derived from the ladder of participation (Arnstein, 1969; see also Dijkstra et al, 2012), and ranged from having read about SPIs, searching for information, discussing SPIs with others, participating in a workshop before or organised a workshop. Participants were free to leave the question open (without experience) or answer as they saw fit. They could give more answers. See Table 14. In total, 15 answers were received from participants who had read about SPIs in the past. Furthermore, participants answered 10 times to have searched for SPIs, and 4 times to have discussed the topic, while 3 answers were given that participation in another workshop had taken place. No participants had organised a workshop about SPIs before.. Answers between the countries differ and are not directly comparable due to the different number of respondents per country. As with the EWs, more passive experience with SPIs (have read, searched, or discussed) was reported than active experience with SPIs (have participated or organised).

Table 14: Type of experience	Italy (N=9)	Portugal (N=6)	Spain (N=4)	Belgium (N=2)
I have read about SPIs in the past	8	3	3	1
I have searched for SPIs online or in other sources	4	2	3	1
I have discussed SPIs with others	3		1	
I have participated in a workshop about SPIs before	2		1	
I have organised workshops about SPIs before				

Finally, the participants were asked if these experiences had influenced them in some way (see Table 15, below). They were asked to answer four questions: whether these experiences changed their views on science journalism or science communication; have proven useful for work, influenced their professional attitude, or contributed to more confidence in professional competencies. They could answer on a five-point Likert-scale ranging from 'not at all' to 'a great deal'. Various respondents did not fill in this question which means that reporting means and standard deviation provides only limited insights, and that interpretation should be considered with caution. In *Italy*, mostly answers were received which were around the mid-point of the scale. In *Portugal* and *Spain*, four respondents filled in the questions. While in *Belgium*, the two respondents provided answers. To sum up, the means indicate that past experiences changed the views of the participants to a moderate amount in *Italy* and a little in *Belgium*, *Spain* and *Portugal*. These experiences were reported as 'have proven useful' to a moderate amount in *Italy* and *Portugal*, and a little in *Spain* and *Belgium*. The same pattern is visible for influence on professional attitude. Finally, more confidence in professional competencies were reported with a moderate amount for *Italy*, and a little for *Belgium*, *Spain* and *Portugal*. In sum, modest influence is reported from past experiences with SPIs.

Table 15: Influence of experiences	Italy (N=9)	Portugal (N=4)	Spain (N=4)	Belgium (N=11)
<i>My experiences with SPIs in the past...</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>
... changed my views on science journalism and science communication	2.67 (1.15)	2.00 (0.63)	2.30 (1.00)	1.92 (1.19)
... have proven useful in my work	3.33 (0.67)	2.90 (1.22)	2.20 (1.08)	2.55 (1.37)
... influence my professional attitude	3.33 (0.94)	2.90 (1.22)	2.40 (1.28)	2.55 (1.37)
... contributed to more confidence in my professional competences	3.11 (0.99)	2.30 (1.10)	2.30 (1.19)	2.18 (1.11)

Views on science journalism and science communication

ENJOI - ENgagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication

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www.enjoiscicomm.eu

The participants from the Labs were asked about their views on science journalism and science communication with two questions. The first question asked to describe good quality science journalism and science communication with the help of three key words. The second question explored views on trust with four statements. The question with the statements about good science journalism or science communication was left out because at the moment of the Labs there was already a first draft of key SPIs formulated which the participants had received before the Lab. Adding the question would then interfere with the intended discussion during the Lab.

From all the keywords together one word-cloud was produced which is shown in figure 5. Clearly, clarity and rigour were the most prominent. Other keywords related to truth, correctness, engagement, simple, sources, objectivity and attention for sources as well as accountability. These keywords are comparable to those mentioned before the EWs, e.g. clarity and rigour, and generally, these relate to the list of SPIs as it was developed in the EWs.

Regarding trust, the table 16 below presents the results on views of trust in science journalism and science communication. The reported means are high and mostly above the mid-point scale in all countries. Thus, trust is higher when ‘the topic is presented from different perspectives’, ‘when reporters are knowledgeable about the topic’ and ‘the communication about the topic is transparent’. For the statement ‘interests of stakeholders are reported’ some answers are a bit lower. The pattern with the means from the Labs is

comparable to the answers provided during the EWs. So, generally speaking, trust in science journalism and science communication relates to showing different perspectives, reporting interests of various stakeholders, knowledge from the reporters about the topic, and transparency in the communication.

Table 16: Trust in science journalism and science communication	Italy (N=11)	Portugal (N=6)	Spain (N=4)	Belgium (N=2)
<i>I trust science journalism and science communication when ...</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>
... the topic is presented from different perspectives	4.09 (0.51)	4.00 (0.65)	5.00 (0.00)	3.50 (0.50)
... interests of stakeholders are reported	3.18 (0.86)	4.29 (0.45)	4.50 (0.50)	3.50 (0.50)
... reporters are knowledgeable about the topic	4.27 (0.86)	3.86 (0.91)	4.75 (0.43)	4.50 (0.50)
... the communication about the topic is transparent	4.45 (0.89)	5.00 (0.00)	5.00 (0.00)	4.50 (0.50)

Expectations about the outcomes and impact

As in the EWs, expectations about the outcomes were asked with three statements whether respondents could relate outcomes to their own work, outcomes would make sense, and outcomes would be used for the next step in the project. In Table 17 the responses are provided. Generally, high agreement was reported, since participants in *all countries* agreed to a large degree with all three statements.

Table 17: Expectations about outcomes	Italy (N=10)	Portugal (N=6)	Spain (N=3)	Belgium (N=2)
<i>I expect that ...</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>
... I can relate outcomes of the workshop to my own work	4.00 (0.77)	4.17 (0.69)	4.67 (0.33)	4.00 (0.00)
... the outcomes will make sense to me	3.80 (1.08)	4.33 (0.75)	5.00 (0.00)	4.00 (0.00)
... the outcomes will be used for the next step in the project	4.30 (0.64)	4.83 (0.37)	5.00 (0.00)	4.50 (0.50)

In addition, views on engaging stakeholders in general and impact were asked with four statements. These were 'it makes sense to consider input from stakeholders such as myself', 'it can inspire new outcomes', 'it will be informative but with little impact' and 'I expect that suggestions formulated in the workshop will serve as relevant input for the upcoming activities'. High means are also reported for three of the four questions in *all countries* in the Labs. This means that participants agreed to a large extent with these

statements. However, as in the EWs, participants in *all four countries* were more neutral to the statement that ‘it will be informative but with little impact’ (except in Spain). In Spain answers were just below the mid-point of the scale which can be interpreted as that they were not sure about the impact. As also indicated with the EWs, the statement leaves room for multiple interpretations which makes the exact meaning unclear.

Table 18: Views on engaging stakeholders and impact	Italy (N=10)	Portugal (N=6)	Spain (N=4)	Belgium (N=2)
<i>In general, what is your view on engaging stakeholders in such a workshop?</i>	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
It makes sense to consider input from stakeholders such as myself	4.40 (0.66)	4.83 (0.37)	5.00 (0.00)	4.50 (0.50)
It can inspire new outcomes	4.40 (0.66)	4.83 (0.37)	4.50 (0.50)	4.50 (0.50)
It will be informative but with little impact	2.60 (1.02)	2.83 (1.34)	4.75 (0.43)	2.00 (0.00)
I expect that suggestions formulated in the workshop will serve as relevant input for the upcoming activities	4.10 (0.70)	4.50 (0.76)	5.00 (0.00)	4.50 (0.50)

Additionally, in one combined open question participants’ professional and personal expectations were asked. In *Italy* expectations were to improve knowledge, communication skills and grow professionally. Furthermore, to network but also to contribute to the discussions for a better science communication. In *Portugal* increasing knowledge, learning better science communication and improving one's own skills were mentioned as well as to contribute and listen to different perspectives. In *Spain* similar expectations were given as to apply the learnings to work, to learn, improve and contribute and also interact with other professionals. In *Belgium*, finally, better knowledge to measure output of science communication was expected.

3.4 Results from the Lab interviews

After the Labs interviews were conducted. In a first round, in total four interviews were held. Thematic analysis was applied and based on main themes, sub-themes emerged, similar to those from the interviews after the EWs. Results from the observation forms are included in the reporting and provided more context as well.

Contexts of the Labs

The first Lab was held in Italy on 27 October 2022 and included 10 participants. The first Lab was addressing citizens and organisations representing citizens which meant that the

participants' background varied as is described above. The atmosphere during the Lab can be described as collaborative and focused. However, there was a feeling of pressure since time was too short to be able to read the SPIs and reflect on what was read. The background of the interviewee from Italy was in philosophy and special needs education. According to this interviewee, interest in science communication related to his interest as a citizen, and the interviewee stated that science should be open to citizens while they should be able to and have the right to make well-informed decisions. In sum, knowing about science is a democratic right, according to this interviewee.

The second Lab was organized in Portugal on 9 November 2022, and 13 researchers participated in this meeting. Based on the experienced time constraints in the first Lab, the schedule in Portugal was adapted. Participants had more time to read and, within their groups, only needed to read and reflect on one part of the SPIs. The atmosphere was described as relaxed, constructive and very focused on the work to be done. Participants were actively involved in constructive discussions and could critically review the SPIs. General feedback from the participants was they enjoyed the Lab. In general, there was more time for participants to discuss their ideas. However, during the tools phase, when some participants had to leave, a feeling of rush during the co-designing of the tools was observed. In Portugal, one interview was scheduled but the participant did not show up or answer emails thereafter. Other participants did not respond as well. Therefore, no interviews could be held. A reason may be the work pressure at the research institutes they work at.

The Lab in Spain was organised on 28 November 2022. In total, 11 participants with a background in science communication and science journalism joined and contributed to the Lab. Also, three participants from the EW participated again. The interaction during the Lab was described as synergetic. The participants were dedicated and enthusiastic. It was a challenge to ensure that the participants could contribute to all steps within the time frame available. But generally, it was an effective, direct and enjoyable workshop. The two interviewees had a background in science communication as communication officer and one as science journalist working in a small organisation on science journalism.

Finally, the Lab in Belgium on 7 December 2022 was organised online to accommodate that policy makers and decision makers were able to participate. Eight people participated in the beginning, however, only five could stay till the end and, therefore, could actively contribute. The atmosphere was described as cooperative, engaged and

thought-provoking. Everyone was motivated and engaged with the topic which led to interesting debates. One interview was conducted with an interviewee working as a citizen science advisor with a background in physics and managing various citizen science projects.

Theme 1: Evaluation of the Engagement Workshops

Regarding **expectations** of interviewees, one interviewee expected a good workshop because the organiser is capable of doing so and expectations were met. According to one interviewee, the online Lab was interesting with relevant discussions. The interviewee did not have time to read the materials in detail beforehand. That it was online was appreciated because it allows different people to be present and enabled including a broader and international perspective. Another interviewee did not have a clear expectation beforehand, but also enjoyed the Lab much which had a positive and interesting atmosphere where it was possible to exchange ideas about communication, biases and more topics related to science communication. These views are in line with those of the other two interviewees.

In general, all interviewees went to the Labs with an *open mind* and reported *pleasant atmospheres*, interactive Labs that were *organised professionally* with deep and interesting discussions, which was one of the observations from the Labs as well. As one interviewee explained, the Lab was intellectually stimulating and it was interesting to meet other people either online or in person. Regarding the *organisation and experiences* during the workshops, the interviewees reported good experiences with the organisation. All agreed that the Labs were very well organised, including the online Lab.

When asked for *improvements*, interviewees mentioned time constraints. In the first Lab in Italy, a lot of input was requested which wasn't always easy, although the discussion was much appreciated (L1). After the adaptation of the design of the subsequent Labs, time constraints were still mentioned, but also that interviewees were willing to spend a whole day in the workshop, and suggested either multiple meetings or a longer workshop. However, not all participants would have had time or possibility to do, was expected (L3, L4). Also for the online Lab, a series of meetings were suggested (L2). Otherwise, the organisation of the Lab was experienced as good and leading to in-depth discussions and thinking about principles, standards and indicators and their importance in the field of science journalism and science communication.

Generally, **engagement** was found to be a very positive element and interviewees felt

engaged. One interviewee formulated it as feeling engaged and valued for giving opinions, and the Lab offered a safe space to do so. On the more general question about engagement, they brought in that engagement is really important to get different points of view. It is considered beneficial to work together and have a peer collaboration.

Finally, regarding engagement in relation to **improving the field of science communication**, one interviewee related engagement to responsibility. When there is a possibility for engagement, also there is a responsibility to share if someone participates. And, according to this interviewee, if someone does not take responsibility, also participation cannot be shared. It relates to a democratic motivation for science communication, and according to the interviewee, democracy does not mean that someone all the time has to be involved in the actual decision-making. Therefore, in this view, participation and responsibility go together.

Another interviewee agreed that active engagement is only possible with smaller groups. In the organisation, therefore, press releases are sometimes preferred over workshops because more people are reached which means that a different type of impact is reached. The interviewee reflected on a discussion about impact, with measuring a number of likes or similar as being a metric rather than impact. However, the impact of workshops is not measurable in a direct way, that is, the effects of a workshop on health style are not identifiable after a few years when other activities can also have had an impact. For example, how to follow up on a group of students after different years. As the interviewee said, 'we should work to find an effective way of measuring impact'.

Theme 2: Views on quality of science journalism and science communication

The second theme deals with views on what entails quality science journalism or science communication. On the first question about views on SPIs after the Lab. The first interviewee found the SPIs *useful for many different groups*, in different *roles* (L1). SPIs can be used as a *checklist*, for example, to see how one can improve science communication. Also, funders could use the list as a *guideline for criteria for funding*. Furthermore, there is **not one set of standards, principles and indicators** which are good for everyone. These best could be *used as a guideline or guidance*. Implementation via a checklist for projects and for funding calls could make the criteria for funding more concrete. What surprised one interviewee was that, in general, the SPIs were broad and covered much. And from the perspective of, for example, a journalist different concerns would be applicable than for funders, and the discussion delivered new viewpoints to the interviewee.

Another interviewee (L3) said that the SPIs covered all the aspects that the interviewee considers important. The fear this interviewee uttered is that, in the end, the SPIs will not be applied. It would be recommendable to have the SPIs and the accompanying guidelines to move forward and achieve impact. Because, according to the interviewee, science communication is like a service to society and science journalists are there to inform but not to influence society. And to give them the tools to make informed decisions about, for example, health and the environment. Suggestions to implementation are to make a good campaign to spread the word. What sometimes happens, according to the interviewee, is that science journalists believe they apply the criteria but in practice improvement on points is possible. Therefore, a type of practical training would also be recommended. Also for students and researchers, in every stage of their careers.

From a science journalism perspective, another interviewee added that applying principles in the field of journalism is very challenging because journalists have to work super fast. Principles offer structure and a way to see science communication. Guidelines for SPIs can therefore be useful, in particular when journalists don't have time to remember all SPIs when doing their work. Such a list can be very helpful. Principles can be used in work, in daily work, according to the interviewee. All principles make sense, but in practice, probably, only two will be implemented in the daily work. Journalists are not easy on accepting mistakes.

Finally, one interviewee said that SPIs are a good means to clarify the quality of science communication (L2). This interviewee expected to be able to use them in practice. For example, by taking some content of science and checking whether it meets the standards, principles and indicators, comparable to the European framework. According to the interviewee, the EU framework is also difficult to implement in practice. Providing some good and some bad examples may be helpful, was suggested.

Quality of science communication, according to one interviewee (L1), is connected to correctness and clearness. It is difficult to find a balance between these two and make them both scientifically correct. For example, to make things easy enough for a very broad target group to understand it, applied to climate change, to communicate about the uncertainties and not knowing for sure what the data mean, and still be very clear about how pressing the issue is. Climate change is intertwined with very different aspects which increases the complexity of communication while there is not one solution possible. In

those cases, indicators related to the accuracy of reporting and transparency, like openness about sources, are important, agreed the interviewee.

Or, as another interviewee found (L3), quality is important because, in the end, science journalism is a kind of service towards society. Communication needs to be rigorous, for example. The interviewee gave an example of a press release about a study in mice which was taken up in the media and was presented in the media as having a cure for food issues. It is important to educate the audience and the journalist. However, also research centres oversell their research findings and make them too sensationalist. Sometimes, in press releases, too many promises are made. According to the interviewee, caution in presenting results is needed. It is recommended to be careful with expectations which can be derived from the results.

Furthermore, the rise of social media (for example, the Internet, Google, YouTube or Instagram) also enhanced the possibility of spreading misinformation. Therefore, *education of science communicators* can help, but also of citizens so they can detect this type of information correctly. For example, in workshops for secondary school students, they can be trained and made aware of the issues with misinformation. It is possible to ask them what is reliable information. Even the interviewee mentioned issues with identifying what is the correct information. One of the interviewees, however, suggested that an important principle for good quality science communication may be accuracy. Finally, the last interviewee said that the independence of the researcher is most important. Independence, both from the institution as well as from the audience. And also transparency and other standards were discussed.

Regarding **reliability and trust**, for some interviewees trust was the term, while others referred to reliability. According to the first interviewee (L1), good science communication should increase trust. If there is no trust, maybe science communication is not enough, and one should do other things first to build some basic level of trust before science communication can have any effect. There is only so much that science communication can do for the non-believers and the really sceptical people. Science communication cannot solve everything. In one project, this interviewee specifically aims for people who say that technology is not for them. In the activities, first, they try to get them to talk more about societal issues, or work topics, and issues they have with their environment, traffic or health. The questions start with asking what topics people are concerned about. And then, they slowly bring in the topic of technology (in this case AI). In the beginning, the team

made the mistake of starting from the technology which meant that people were already running away before the story could start. Such an approach, however, is very labour-intensive and takes a lot of time, and cannot be done with large groups of 10,000 people. It works only with smaller groups.

In addition, several times it was said that trust is easier broken down than gained. One example, mentioned by an interviewee (L1), experiences from an AI project was that, first, trust is built by starting from the audience's experiences and their stories, and connect with what they do in daily life. The aim, ultimately, is that they help the researchers with coming up with new AI solutions they need. It is really about creating a dialogue together with your audiences.

Another interviewee (L3) suggested on the question of reliability, to build a kind of brand reputation (as institutes or universities) and maintain that next to training audiences. If one university spreads misinformation that will have an effect on other universities as well. Mistrust can easily build up. And, science communicators have the task of building trust-relations with society and being careful with the reputations of universities. For the trust, it is important not to only show the final results but also the process. Researchers are still not fully able to communicate the process of science, according to the interviewee. Furthermore, engagement is key to improving insights into science communication and improving trust in science communication.

Finally, another interviewee (L4) summarized it as that trust in science will lead to people making better decisions, based on information and facts. In journalism, the journalists are helping with the facts and letting people know all the facts. Also, facts will make better political decisions. In both the pandemic and vaccinations it was clear that it is important that people know how science works and how making a vaccine works. This interviewee also acknowledges that it is a dilemma because facts are the result. At the same time, open science is to be considered as communication about a project. Finally, reliability was mainly considered by this interviewee (L4) as the reliability of the scientist, and a scientist becomes reliable after a while. This interviewee also believes that researchers should get the opportunity to prove themselves to be reliable. Thus, reliability is a value that has always to be controlled and checked.

4. DISCUSSION

In this section, a discussion of the findings derived from the questionnaires, the observation forms and the interviews from both the Engagement Workshops and the Labs are discussed and limitations are presented.

Summary and discussion of the findings

For the continuous evaluation, a mixed method approach was applied to, first, collect data about the engagement processes during the two series of activities, and second, data about participants' (changing) views about quality science journalism and science communication. These data were collected with questionnaires beforehand, interviews afterwards and findings from observation forms. In this section, the findings are summarized and discussed.

Evaluation of the series of activities and engagement processes more generally

In the **series of Engagement Workshops (EWs)**, a rich variety of people participated who had different backgrounds and varied experiences, both in duration and across domains of science journalism and science communication. Their variety of experiences enabled us to collect broad and nuanced views. As a group, they had ample experience with traditional, institutional and social media. Their expectations *beforehand*, about the outcomes and impact, showed consistently, across the four countries, that they expected outcomes that could be related to improving their own work. Furthermore, the outcomes would make sense and would be used as further input for the project. More generally, engaging stakeholders in such workshops would make sense, can inspire new outcomes and be expected to deliver relevant input. The findings for the statement that engagement of stakeholders would be informative but with little impact could not be interpreted correctly since the statement held a dual message. Finally, expectations from open questions were that participants were expected to broaden their perspectives, exchange experiences, meet others from the field or outside the field, and learn from the workshop and discussions which would motivate and inspire them.

In the series of **Labs**, representatives of different quadruple helix stakeholder groups, including citizens participated. Similar expectations about outcomes and impact were given. In addition, professional and personal expectations aligned with those from the EWs.

Findings from the observations and the interviews **after the EWs** show that expectations of the participants were largely met. In particular, the dynamics of the co-creation

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methodology were experienced as very engaging. The timing of the EWs, for many participants the first in-person meetings after several lockdowns, surely contributed to the enthusiastic responses. When probed to suggest improvements, suggestions such as exchanging experiences between groups, measuring the impact of the workshops, as well as organising means to meet and share insights from the EWs (e.g. meetings, trainings or setting up a community of practice), were given. The participants regarded the background of the individual members of the groups as complementary to each other, while input from more (science) journalists or, for example, newsrooms or directors, was welcomed, in particular in Belgium, Portugal and to a lesser extent in Spain.

Engagement was considered by some interviewees as the only way to learn from each other, and more generally, the engagement activities, including the process and outcomes were highly appreciated and considered a fruitful means to reflect and learn from discussions. The engagement was said to contribute to their professional development. Listening to other participants with different backgrounds, as sources of consultation, and discussing views with them were considered important. In particular, participants with a (science) journalism background mentioned that workshops, as the ones they participated in, were valued as a means to discuss, reflect, and meet others, and contributed to their professional development. Science communication participants referred more often to training or courses as a means for professionalisation.

Findings from the **Labs** from the interviews show also expectations of good workshops and meeting others. Participants went with an open mind and reported pleasant atmospheres and had interesting discussions which were intellectually stimulating. They found the Labs well-organised as well. Also, the online Lab received positive remarks. Improvements related to time constraints. In particular, during the first Lab in Italy, time pressure was experienced during the exercises to read and improve the draft version of the SPIs. Also, after the amendment of the consecutive Labs, some time constraints for this part of the workshop were mentioned. However, some interviewees said to be willing to spend more time in such workshops. Engagement, as in the EWs, was considered a positive element and they felt engaged and valued for sharing opinions. A constraint of engagement that was noted was that such processes are only possible with smaller groups which is why, in practice, organisations fall often back on less engaging communication means such as press releases.

In sum, it can be concluded that the engagement processes, via the series of co-creation

workshops, are relevant and effective means to work on a topic in-depth. The co-creation methods enabled fruitful discussions which led to more insight into the working mechanisms of science journalism and science communication while at the same time, relevant input was given to the development of the standards, principles and indicators. The workshops were professionally organised. Therefore, the engagement process with co-creation methods can be recommended as stimulating to explore and develop criteria for quality science journalism and science communication.

Similar experiences about co-creation and participation were reported in other co-creation projects such as the GoNano project (cf. Schuurbiens et al, 2019). In addition, in Deliverable 3.5 (Zolotonosa et al, 2023), eight findings on the engagement process were reported which included that the approach helped ensure that all participants had their say. Furthermore, it used diversity to enrich the process and helped to achieve a lot in a short space of time, although some parts of the approach needed to be built in more time. More concrete examples could have strengthened the approach while the format in itself strengthened dialogue. Finally, participants appreciated the focus on sharing and networking but a better follow-up was also appreciated. Future co-creation processes around excellence in science communication such as those in the COALESCE project can certainly draw on these findings, something that will be facilitated by the role of ENJOI partners in this and other ongoing and future initiatives.

Evaluation of views on quality science journalism and science communication

Related to the quality of science journalism and science communication, **beforehand**, about half of the participants in the EWs in all countries reported a little or a moderate amount of experience with SPIs, with a few participants reporting more experience, and the other half reporting no experiences at all. Put on a so-called 'ladder of participation' (cf. Arnstein, 1975; Dijkstra et al, 2012), those experiences related mainly to more passive forms of experiences, that is, to reading about, searching for, or discussing SPIs. A few participants reported active experiences as participating in a workshop about SPIs before and organising one. Mostly, those previous experiences had had a modest influence on the participants' professional attitude, confidence in competencies, usefulness for work, or views on science journalism and science communication.

The EWs participants' views on science journalism and science communication with keywords were reflected in the words *clarity*, *understandable*, and *rigour*, while other words, such as honesty, transparency, sources, languages and target audience were mentioned as

well. Responses to statements about good science journalism and science communication showed high agreement, within all countries, that multiple sources, openness and more experience with reporting from science sources or media producers lead to improvement of science journalism and science communication. Meanwhile, statements about independence from the speed of reporting or the media type and dependence on the background of the media producer mainly received neutral support. Finally, participants in all countries agreed highly that they trusted science journalism and science communication when the topic was presented from different perspectives, stakeholders' interests were reported (with the exception of Italian participants), reporters were knowledgeable, and the communication was transparent.

Results from all countries from the **Labs** show that experiences with SPIs were similarly distributed as for the EWs, although in some countries (Spain and Belgium), fewer participants filled in the questionnaires. That is, about two-thirds of the participants reported some experience or more, and about one-third reported no experience. This experience consisted – as was found for the EWs – mainly of reading, searching for, and, to a lesser extent, discussing SPIs with others. Some participants had participated in the EWs before. Those past experiences influenced them to a modest extent.

The most prominent key-words that reflected the Labs participant's views on science journalism and science communication were *clearly*, *clarity* and *rigour*. Their views on what entailed trust were comparable to views of the EWs participants. And the participants from the Labs in all countries highly agreed that trust related to presenting different perspectives, reporting the interests of stakeholders, knowledgeable reporters as well as transparent communication. The question with statements about good science journalism and science communication was not asked in order to not interfere with the working on the SPIs during the Lab.

Afterwards, findings from the *observations and the interviews after the EWs*, about views on the quality of science journalism and science communication differed between those interviewees with a (science) journalism background compared to those with a (science) communication background. Both fields were distinguished by the participants as prioritising different criteria for quality. As was argued, for all subdomains of science communication, different criteria would apply, and, consequently, SPIs have a different meaning in science journalism as in science communication (as in other domains) and therefore, standards cannot work as a standard for all. However, for example, some

standards may align. SPIs were considered a good instrument to define a framework from where to work, and SPIs can uplift quality.

For *science communication*, the standards or principles *understandable, correct and simplifying scientific information* reflect quality. Also, *reliability, trustworthiness and openness* were discussed. Putting information in context and taking multiple aspects into account were mentioned as important. Various interviewees brought up discussions about objectivity and subjectivity, with some arguing that objectivity can not be obtained and others that communicating science should be based on facts and be as objective as possible. Reliability and trust are sometimes seen as synonymous, but not by all interviewees. In addition, that trust needs to be built up was discussed. Other quality criteria that were discussed were honesty and transparency. Honesty towards audiences can be measured via sources or multiple voices in a message. Another standard or principle that was brought up is accuracy.

Standards or principles for *science journalism* were transparency, reliability of the information, sources and formats. Respect for audiences or the public, for example, respecting their previous knowledge, was discussed and considered a different aspect than trust. Furthermore, and most importantly, clarity and rigour were discussed as the main standards. Another task is to provide context.

Concerning reliability and transparency, the risk of *source intimacy* was brought up (cf. Dunwoody, 2022). It means that too close relationships between journalists and scientists can affect trust in scientific information as journalists cannot always criticise the researchers' work. At the same time, sometimes research institutes prepare ready-made press releases, which also include quotes, to ease the workload for journalists since their workload is so high. This example fits with the trend of medialisation of science (Franzen et al, 2012), which is a process where researchers and their institutes increasingly try to get their results communicated via media. Openness about ready-made information can support journalists in considering whether to use that information. Balance and avoiding *false balance* were both brought up as well (see Boycoff & Boycoff, 2004) and were related to ideas about the tasks of journalists as having to fight disinformation. Within participants with a fact-checking background, this was mentioned several times.

Finally, within the journalism profession, often ethical codes or guidelines exist and are discussed in, for example, newsrooms or, for freelancers, between peers. Such discussions

increase awareness about professional development. Also, within journalism, perspectives on what objectivity and subjectivity are were discussed. Objective reporting, as was argued, is never possible because the choice of questions determine the perspective on a topic. Reliability relates to referring to scientific data, which can be achieved by adding original sources or links to supporting documents.

In the interviews after the Labs, the SPIs were discussed as being useful for different groups, and these can be used as a checklist or guideline for funding. Therefore, these SPIs should be promoted and boosted and training could be developed. And it was also said that not one set of SPIs is good for everyone. Some concern about the application of the SPIs in practice was raised. More generally, in the science journalism field, the application of SPIs in practice is challenging and often is limited to only one or two standards or principles.

Limitations

Limitations of the evaluation methods also have to be acknowledged. The nature of the series of EWs and Labs can and did only attract a limited number of participants. It means that the data from the questionnaires should be interpreted with care. Additionally, in Spain and Belgium, fewer participants filled in the questionnaire which was distributed before the Lab. Careful consideration also applies to the interpretation of the interview data. In particular, interpretation from the Lab interviewees was not easy to arrange, which led to fewer interviewees than anticipated. Although findings align much with those from the EW interviews, the qualitative nature of the data is to be considered.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this section, conclusions are drawn and recommendations are formulated as input for the [ENJOI Observatory](#) for Outstanding Science Communication. These recommendations relate to the engagement process and co-creation methods and the quality of science journalism and science communication.

Conclusions

First of all, it can be concluded that engagement as a method, as was applied in the workshops, was appreciated by both participants and the organisers of the activities. The activities were professionally executed. Insights can inspire future co-creation workshops.

Second, the insights from the both series of activities, enabled us to collect detailed and rich findings which formed the basis for the SPIs. The list of SPIs can be used as a guideline for experts in the fields of science journalism and science communication. Findings also show that the list of SPIs can best be tailored to each group by offering a different prioritisation of standards and principles. Generally, the list of SPIs are considered a useful means to reflect on quality within both fields of science journalism and science communication. Science journalists prefer to reflect on quality in discussions in newsrooms, with peers or via workshops. Science communicators more often refer to training and courses as means to consider quality and improve the profession.

Recommendations about engagement and quality of science journalism and science communication

Finally, recommendations are formulated for the ENJOI Observatory, which are:

- To share experiences of the co-creation workshops with future users
- To organise engagement processes with co-creation methods as a relevant and effective means to work on a topic in an in-depth way.
- To share learnings from the ENJOI engagement workshops and labs to design future engagement activities.
- To promote the use of SPIs as a guideline for reflection and discussion of the quality of science journalism and science communication.
- To distinguish between the field of science journalism and science communication and allow adaptation of the list of SPIs for the different domains.
- To develop different types of trainings for both the science journalism and the science communication domains.
- To stimulate reflection and discussion about quality in science journalism by means of workshops and boardroom meetings so journalists can fit it in their workload.

- To stimulate reflection and discussion about quality in science communication by means of trainings and courses for science communicators and researchers.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A Questionnaire for EW or Lab

Aims	
<i>Aims of the EW</i>	<i>Co-creating principles; Identifying standards; Defining indicators</i>
<i>Aims of the questionnaire</i>	<i>To collect additional information about:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>o Views about SPIs</i> <i>o How the EWs contribute to quality and reliability of science communication</i> <i>o How mechanisms of multi-stakeholder engagement help to improve science communication</i> <i>o How mechanisms for multi-stakeholder engagement that aim to create and promote trustworthy science communication work</i>

Topic	Question	Comments
Language selection	You can select the language of your choice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Dutch <input type="radio"/> English <input type="radio"/> French <input type="radio"/> Italian <input type="radio"/> Portuguese <input type="radio"/> Spanish 	
	In which Engagement Workshop / Lab will you participate? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Belgium <input type="radio"/> Italy <input type="radio"/> Portugal <input type="radio"/> Spain 	
<i>Socio-demographic</i>	What is the age group you are in? I'm between: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> 18 and 24 years <input type="radio"/> 25 and 34 years <input type="radio"/> 35 and 44 years <input type="radio"/> 45 and 54 years <input type="radio"/> 55 and 64 years <input type="radio"/> Above 65 years 	
	What is the gender you identify with? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to say <input type="radio"/> Non-binary / third gender <input type="radio"/> Female <input type="radio"/> Male 	
	What is the highest level of education you completed? I completed a: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Lower level of education <input type="radio"/> Middle level of education <input type="radio"/> Higher level of education 	

<i>Stakeholders</i>	How many years of experience do you have in the field of science journalism and science communication? <input type="radio"/> None at all <input type="radio"/> Less than 1 year <input type="radio"/> Between 1 and 5 years <input type="radio"/> Between 5 and 10 years <input type="radio"/> More than 10 years	
<i>Role of the stakeholder</i>	How would you describe your role or roles in science journalism or science communication in a few words? Lab: how would you describe your professional background / role? I'm a:	Word cloud
	Which type of media are you engaged with? Engaged with can be broadly defined as: writing for, post on, using for work, collaborate with, et cetera. More than one answer is possible: <input type="radio"/> Traditional media, namely: <input type="radio"/> TV <input type="radio"/> Radio <input type="radio"/> News paper <input type="radio"/> Institutional media, namely: ... <input type="radio"/> Social media, namely: <input type="radio"/> Twitter <input type="radio"/> Snapchat <input type="radio"/> LinkedIn <input type="radio"/> Facebook <input type="radio"/> Website <input type="radio"/> Other... <input type="radio"/> None of these	
	In the ENJOI project we aim to improve our understanding of what makes good science journalism and science communication by making it more consistently, reliable, truthful, open and engaging. The following questions explore your views.	
<i>Good science communication</i>	With three key words: what would characterise good science journalism or science communication to you? <input type="radio"/> Key word 1: <input type="radio"/> Key word 2: <input type="radio"/> Key word 3:	Word cloud of the words given. We can make different word clouds for each EW and Lab
<i>Role SPIs</i>	In the workshop standards, principles and indicators (SPIs) for good science journalism and science communication will be discussed. How much experience do you have with SPIs separately or the three together? <input type="radio"/> None at all <input type="radio"/> A little <input type="radio"/> A moderate amount <input type="radio"/> A lot	Translation of: [strongly disagree, somewhat disagree, neither disagree or agree, somewhat agree, strongly agree] Translation of: [not at all, a little, a moderate

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o A great deal <p>Can you specify?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o I have read about SPIs in the past o I have searched for SPIs online or in other sources o I have discussed SPIs with others o I have participated in a workshop about SPIs before o I have organised workshops about SPIs before o None of the above (if this answer is given, the following question will be skipped) <p>Please answer on a scale from not at all to a great deal.</p> <p>My experiences with SPIs in the past ...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o changed my views on science journalism and science communication o have proven useful in my work o influenced my professional attitude o contributed to more confidence in my professional competences 	amount, a lot, a great deal]
	<p>To what extent do you agree with the following statements?</p> <p>Please answer on a scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. [only in EW questionnaire]</p> <p>Good science journalism and science communication ...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o improves when multiple sources are used o improves when openness about the sources is given o is independent from the speed of reporting o depends mainly on the background of the media producer o is independent from the media type o improves when science sources have more experience with reporting o improves when media producers have more experience <p>I trust science journalism and science communication, when...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o the topic is presented from different perspectives o interests of stakeholders are reported o reporters are knowledgeable about the topic o the communication about the topic is transparent 	
<i>Expectations of the contribution of the workshop to the engagement process</i>	<p>To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the engagement workshop?</p> <p>Please answer on a scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree.</p> <p>I expect that ...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o I can relate outcomes of the workshop to my own work o The outcomes will make sense to me o The outcomes will be used for the next step in the 	

	<p>project</p> <p>In general, what is your view on engaging stakeholders in such a workshop?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o It makes sense to consider input from stakeholders such as myself o It can inspire new outcomes o It will be informative but with little impact o I expect that suggestions formulated in the workshop will serve as relevant input for the upcoming activities 	
	<p>What professional outcome do you aim for when participating in the workshop? Please describe ...</p> <p>What personal outcome do you aim for when participating in the workshop? Please describe... [combined in Lab]</p>	
	<p>Finally, would you have any suggestions or comments? Please describe ...</p>	
	<p>Thank you for filling in this questionnaire. The outcomes will inform the project.</p>	

APPENDIX B Interview template for EW or Lab

Aims		
<i>Aims of the EW</i>	<i>Co-creating principles; Identifying standards; Defining indicators</i>	
<i>Aims of the observation</i>	<p><i>To collect additional information about:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o <i>Views about SPIs</i> o <i>How the EWs contribute to quality and reliability of science communication</i> o <i>How mechanisms of multi-stakeholder engagement help to improve science communication</i> o <i>How mechanisms work for multi-stakeholder engagement that aim to create and promote trustworthy science communication</i> 	
Topic	Question	Comments
<i>Socio-demographic</i>	What is your age?	
	With what gender do you identify yourself?	
	In which EW or Lab did you participate?	Can be filled in by the interviewer
<i>Stakeholders</i>	How much experience do you have in the field of science communication and science journalism?	(a bit repetition of the questionnaire but useful to get some context information for the interview)
<i>Role of the stakeholder</i>	<p>What type of stakeholder do you consider yourself?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Science communication o Science journalism o Media producer o Other options <p>What kind of background do you have?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o E.g. a background in journalism or 	Background / role of the stakeholder.

	<p>communication versus a background in sciences or social sciences</p> <p>What type (kind) of media are you involved in? Can you give examples?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Traditional, e.g.... o Institutional, e.g.... o Social, e.g. ... 	
<i>Views on the EW or Lab you were in / Expectations</i>	<p>In the questionnaire you were asked to indicate your expectations of the EW/Lab. Can you repeat very briefly what your expectations were?</p> <p>To what extent were your expectations of the EW/Lab met? Can you explain why or why not?</p> <p>In general, what is your opinion about the EW/Lab you were in?</p> <p>What do you think of the dynamics during the EW/Lab?</p> <p>How would you have improved the EW/Lab?</p>	
<i>Views on SPIs</i>	<p>What is your view on SPIs related to science communication and science journalism after the EW?/ After the Lab?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o General on SPIs ... o Standards ... o Principles ... o Indicators ... <p>Can you explain your views?</p>	
Quality and reliability of science communication?	<p>What defines according to you, after having participated in the EW/Lab, the quality of science communication / science journalism?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o e.g. trust (e.g. in science / scientists / media producers) o transparency (e.g. openness about sources) o accuracy (of reporting / of offering science information) o etc... <p>And what, reliability of science communication / science journalism?</p> <p>How do these two differ, in your view?</p>	
Dynamics of EW engagement	<p>What is your view on the process of engagement during the EW/Lab?</p> <p>In your view, how can such a process of engagement help improve the quality of science communication?</p> <p>In your view, and how can it help improve the reliability of science communication?</p> <p>When do you feel engaged and do you want to participate?</p>	
	<p>What do you think of the partnership that was formed for the workshops?</p> <p>What do you think of the group of stakeholders?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o were any (type of) stakeholders 	

	missing? o would you like to continue?	
	What, do you expect, will be your future engagement in such activities?	
	Finally, what advice would you have for us for the future of science journalism, or more general science communication?	
	Thank you for your participation!	

APPENDIX C Observation template for EW or Lab

Aims	
<i>Aims of the EW</i>	<i>Co-creating principles; Identifying standards; Defining indicators</i>
<i>Aims of the observation</i>	<i>To collect additional information about:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>o Views about SPIs</i> <i>o How the EWs contribute to quality and reliability of science communication</i> <i>o How mechanisms of multi-stakeholder engagement help to improve science communication</i> <i>o How mechanisms work for multi-stakeholder engagement that aim to create and promote trustworthy science communication</i>
Topic	Question
Observer	o Form filled in by:
EW or Lab	o Which EW or Lab did you observe? (date / country) o How many participants participated? o Was the EW or Lab recorded? Yes / no o If yes, the recording is available at: ...
Stakeholders	As far as you know (please NOTE that some background info is asked in the questionnaire so we can derive some info from there as well): o What kind/type of stakeholders participated? o What kind of media did they represent? (traditional / institutional / social) o How many from each group? o What is your general view of the group? o Were any important stakeholders missing? o Were the stakeholders complementary to each other?
Atmosphere	o Can you describe the atmosphere during the meeting in three key words? . good / tensions / other... o Can you briefly explain?
Evaluative questions	o What went well? Please describe a situation (e.g. what, who, what were the outcomes, why do you think it went well?): o What can be improved? How and why? Please describe: o What remark or discussion comes to mind immediately? Please describe:
About the EW	o Can you describe a situation that stood out in a positive way? Please describe:
	o Can you describe a situation that needs more attention a next time?

	Please describe:
Dynamics of the multi-stakeholder engagement	How did the participants contribute to the co-creation of principles, identifying standards or defining indicators? For example, they were active, passive, enthusiastic, reluctant, with hesitancy, dedicated, critical, positive, other Was there one or more contribution of a participant which stood out in a positive or negative way? Please describe:
Reflection	What is a (main) challenge of the SPIs the participants talked about during the EW?
	What is a (main) challenge for the EW seen from the perspective that it is organised as a multi-stakeholder engagement activity?
Suggestions	What suggestion for improvement would you – as an observer – give for the next step in ENJOI? Please describe:
Summary	Can you provide a short summary of the EW with help of a few key words or sentences?

APPENDIX D Informed consent forms

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Information sheet [proposed shorter version]

Why have you been invited to participate?
Based on your expertise and engagement in the field of science communication and science journalism, you have been invited to participate in an online questionnaire to collect data for the Engagement Workshop you are invited to. This workshop is part of the ENJOI project.

What will I have to do if I decide to take part?
Your participation is entirely voluntary and by clicking the link you will consent to take part. You may refuse to take part in the research or exit the survey at any time without penalty or without needing to give a reason. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason.

What will we do with your DATA?
Your responses will be anonymised by removing any personal information and will be analysed alongside other responses to produce aggregate results. All personal data is regulated under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) from the European Union (EU) 2016/679. You can request for all your personal data from all project platforms to be erased at any time. In line with the open access movement, data collected for the project are publicly available in an anonymous form only for use for research purposes. No identifying information will be contained in this dataset.

If it is previously accepted, ENJOI will contact you to inform you about new events, specifically related to ENJOI, or advances on the project.

How can I withdraw?
You can withdraw from the project anytime you decide to, by email to eli@formicablu.it (ENJOI coordinator's email). You do not need to add any explanation of why you want to withdraw from the

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This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement n°101006407
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project. When you withdraw from the study, all your confidential data will be destroyed. If your data has already been analysed, the results will be used but the source of the data will not be retrievable.

There are no direct personal benefits of participation in this study. However, by participating, you will contribute to aims of the ENJOI project, which contributes to the active development of **critical thinking, digital awareness and media literacy** of actors in science communication.

What will be the risks of taking part?

Regarding potential risks, those do not exceed in probability or magnitude the ones that could be expected in a work activity based on agreed meetings (physical and/or online), in which experiences and knowledge are discussed and shared around common projects. Participation in this project is entirely voluntarily and unpaid. Meals are covered, as well as travel expenses when it is necessary to move from one city to another.

Rights and how to exercise them. You have the right to:

- o Request information about whether we have personal data about you, and if so, what information we have, why we have it and how we are using it.
- o Request access to your personal data. This allows you to receive a copy of your personal data and to correct any incomplete or incorrect information.
- o Request personal data deletion. This allows you to delete or ask us to delete your personal data.
- o Request to transfer your personal data to you or to a third party in an electronic and structured format – commonly known as the right to data portability.
- o You can exercise any of these rights by email to eli@formicablu.it
- o You will not have to pay any fee to access your personal data – or to exercise any other of your rights.

If you would like to learn more about the project in general, you can visit our website here: <https://enjoiscicomm.eu/>

We thank you very much for your participation!

With best wishes, researchers on the study
Anne Dijkstra & Anouk de Jong
University of Twente, Science Communication

INFORMED CONSENT FORM for the interview

Why have you been invited to participate?

Based on your expertise and engagement you have been invited to participate in an interview to collect data for the ENJOI project.

What will I have to do if I decide to take part?

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may refuse to take part at any time without penalty or without needing to give a reason. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason.

What will we do with your DATA?

Your responses will be recorded and anonymised by removing any personal information and will be

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analysed alongside other responses to produce aggregate results. All personal data is regulated under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) from the European Union (EU) 2016/679. You can request for all your personal data from all project platforms to be erased at any time. In line with the open access movement, data collected for the project are publicly available in an anonymous form only for use for research purposes. No identifying information will be contained in this dataset.

How can I withdraw?

You can withdraw from the project anytime you decide to, by email to eli@formicablu.it (ENJOI coordinator's email). You do not need to add any explanation of why you want to withdraw from the project. If your data has already been analysed, the results will be used but the source of the data – as it was – will not be retrievable.

There are no direct personal benefits of participation in this study. However, by participating, you will contribute to aims of the ENJOI project, which contributes to the active development of **critical thinking, digital awareness and media literacy** of actors in science communication. There are no particular risks foreseen by participation. Participation in this project is entirely voluntarily.

You can exercise any of the rights as mentioned above by email to eli@formicablu.it

If you would like to learn more about the project in general, you can visit our website here: <https://enjoiscicomm.eu/>

We thank you very much for your participation!

With best wishes, researchers on the study
Anne Dijkstra & Anouk de Jong
University of Twente, Science Communication

By signing you consent to participate in the interview.

Date:

Name & Signature:

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